

Forensic constraints on the tent-site trauma in the Dyatlov incident

(Supplementary Information)

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Introduction

This Supplementary Information provides supporting methodological details and extended data for the accompanying Matters Arising.

Forensic assessments derive exclusively from the 1959 investigation record, with modern trauma physiology (e.g. ATLS) used only to contextualise and confirm the physiological implications already inherent in the 1959 expert's statements.

Walking time estimation relies on a validated modern empirical locomotion model, stated explicitly below.

Time-to-descent components

Digital Elevation Data

All elevation values were extracted from the 2-m ArcticDEM. The DEM was reprojected to UTM Zone 40N (EPSG 32640) to ensure metric accuracy of horizontal distances.

Slope along the tent-to-cedar route was derived from the 2-m ArcticDEM.

Slope Measurement

Slope along the tent-to-cedar transect was computed using the QGIS Profile Tool applied to a straight-line polyline between the tent site and the cedar tree. Local 2-m fluctuations reflect micro-relief and DEM noise ; therefore only aggregated metrics are used to characterise the effective gradient.

The mean downhill slope of the transect is -9.4° .

Walking time estimation model

Walking speed was estimated using the empirical model of Wood et al. (2023), derived from large scale GPS observations of human walking across diverse terrains. The model incorporates terrain obstruction as a categorical variable. This allows assignment to the “heavy-obstruction“ class when the primary-source evidence indicates a deformable surface.

The Wood et al. model predicts walking speed as following:

$$v = \exp(a + b\phi + c\theta + d\theta^2)$$

where

v = walking speed (km/h)

ϕ = hill slope angle (degrees)

θ = walking slope angle (degrees)

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Coefficients for an off-road, heavy-obstruction terrain are:

a = 1.443

b = -0.00731

c = -0.00965

d = -0.00187

Surface classification (heavy-obstruction) followed the criteria and justification provided in the main text, only the numerical implementation is shown here.

Based on average slope (-9.4°), the predicted speed for an uninjured individual is 4.2 km/h, yielding a descent time of 20-21 min (20 min 12 s).

Segment-Level Sensitivity Analysis

To test sensitivity to local variations in slope, the transect was partitioned into four 300-m segments and a final 218-m segment. For each segment mean slope was computed and converted into a predicted walking time using the Wood et al. model.

Table 1 - Predicted Time by Segment

Segment	Elevation from(m)	Elevation to (m)	Slope (°)	Predicted Time
0-300 m	876.24	809.66	-12.51	4 min 37 s
300-600 m	809.66	745.17	-12.13	4 min 33 s
600-900 m	745.17	695.17	-9.46	4 min 17 s
900-1200 m	695.17	652.79	-8.04	4 min 11 s

1200-1418 m	652.79	642.49	-2.7	2 min 59 s
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The total predicted descent time is 20 min 37 s, consistent with the results based on the mean slope.

This analysis shows that plausible segment-to-segment variations do not materially affect the traversal time.

Conclusion

These computations provide the quantitative locomotion baseline needed to assess the feasibility of the 1959 tent-to-cedar descent. All input data (2-m elevation samples) are supplied in `Supplementary_Data_1_Descent_Profile_Coordinates.csv` to ensure full reproducibility.

Forensic constraints table

Extended Data Table 2 (below) compiles for the 3 incapacitated victims found in the ravine:

- (1) the autopsy findings (1959),
- (2) the contemporaneous forensic conclusions recorded in the case file , and
- (3) the corresponding functional implications derived from established modern trauma physiology (e.g. ATLS), which are used solely to express the immediate functional consequences of the injuries described in the 1959 records.

This integrated summary supports the incompatibility between the expected traversal time (20-21 min) and the physiological capacities of Dubinina, Thibeaux-Brignolle and Zolotaryov.

Table 2 - Key autopsy findings (1959)

<i>Victim</i>	<i>Autopsy Findings</i>	<i>Forensic Conclusion (1959)</i>	<i>Functional Implication</i>
Dubinina	Bilateral rib fractures; massive hemothorax; myocardial contusion (right ventricle)	Death in 10-20 min	Massive hemothorax with Class III hemorrhagic shock precludes sustained physical exertion. Predicted descent time (20-21 min) >= documented survival window (10-20 min)
Thibeaux-Brignolle	Basilar skull fracture (temporal, frontal, sphenoid) with	Immediate unconsciousness; could not move even	No voluntary movement possible.

	extensive comminution; massive cerebral oedema.	with assistance.	
Zolotaryov	Rib fractures R2-R6 (mid-sternal and mid-axillary lines); flail chest; 1L hemothorax;	May have lived longer than Dubinina (no functional assessment in 1959 records)	Flail chest and hemothorax cause rapid respiratory compromise; sustained exertion physiologically incompatible.